

A Privacy Risk Dashboard for Clinical Free-text

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Introduction

Providers of health data for research face significant challenges in extracting and linking complex data and safeguarding access by approved researchers. Risk assessments are a key component to ensure that data extracts are processed correctly and do not contain any identifiable patient information. Currently a significant burden is placed on data service teams – including data analysts and information governance specialists – to carry out risk assessment and minimise the risk of patients being identified. Whilst comprehensive systems are in use to support data service teams already, these are primarily manual when it comes to reviewing clinical free-text for privacy risks. This presents significant restrictions on being able to release clinical free-text for research as the process to manually review and check for potential privacy risks is challenging, and therefore very time consuming.

Our work focused on delivering a prototype dashboard that can bring together and visualise privacy risks found in free-text clinical records. The purpose of the dashboard was to support Information Governance (IG) and data analysts within Trusted Research Environments (TRE) at the data access stage in better understanding risks present in a data cohort and to enable proportionate risk-based decisions about data access.

Methods and Data

Initial mock-up designs were done and discussed amongst the team, which included representatives from across the Scottish Safe Havens and facilitated by a specialist design company. Whilst the initial purpose of the prototype is to provide a visual means to explore risks present in a cohort, there are plans for the future to use the App to track and audit the de-risking decisions. For privacy risk assessment, our public involvement activities have emphasised that the use of semi-automation tools should be followed by human checks and monitored using audit trails. Our design process captured the full workflow but we have implemented only the visualising and exploring of privacy risks in the current version, with development done using R Shiny App (see Figure 1 for an example of what this full workflow could look like). Our reasoning behind using R is this is the most universally accepted tool in use within Safe Havens in Scotland not requiring additional approval levels beyond existing mechanisms.

Results

The dashboard tool allows for a cohort to be uploaded, assuming it has been appropriately labelled for risks (see Figure 2 for an example of the tool). The dashboard can be used to understand the types of reports that are in the cohort, sex, age range, ethnicity, and Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) details along with the years range of the reports. Each of these variables can be filtered to rearrange views of the data and of the potential risks. The risks can be viewed based on the filter selection. The report also provides a summary table of these risks which the user can drill down to individual risk types and see how these occur together in a report. The user can also view individual reports with their risk counts as well as rearrange the view to look on a per patient basis and understand cumulative risk. This support Information Governance teams to identify any risk-mitigations steps necessary.

Conclusion

Our privacy risk tool provides a prototype for how we can visualise privacy risks in free text and support those responsible for making decisions about making data extracts available for research. It is a tool that will be built upon in the future and we can see this extended to cohort requests to include both structured and unstructured clinical notes.

Figure 1 Example of workflow of the Risk Management Dashboard

Figure 2 Prototype Privacy Risk Dashboard

Study Context

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